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“TSERA-E2E: ENHANCING EDUCATIONAL OUTCOMES THROUGH INNOVATION”

The project is called **Technology Skills Education Review & Advancement from Enrollment to Employment**, or **TSERA-E2E**. The TVL Specialized track at Paliparan III Senior High School was launched in 2016 as the school's flagship program by founding principal, Mr. Francis Kenneth D. Hernandez and TVL Coordinator and Teacher II, Mr. Francis E. Factura. In accordance with the SHS Curriculum for the K–12 law, or RA No. 10533, this was designed to accommodate the programs and activities for all TVL students. The initiative aims to address the educational needs of learners by implementing a comprehensive framework that integrates several key components:

- After enrolment, TVL students go through **skills training** in order to finish the necessary competencies and required numbers of hours consist of 640 hours in their major courses. These subjects include Electronic Products Assembly and Servicing (EPAS), Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM), Computer System and Servicing (CSS), Cookery-Bread and Pastry Production-Food and Beverage Services (CBF), and Beauty Nail Care Services-Hairdressing-Wellness “Hilot” Massage (BHW).
- Participation in the **DepEd Festival of Talents (Technolympics)** allows students to showcase their skills from the school-based, Division to the Regional, and National levels. At the Division level, all participating learners emerged as champions and advanced to the regional level in the fields of EPAS - 3rd place (2017); BPP, Furniture & Cabinet Making - unplaced (2018); Beauty Care – Champion (2019). At the National level in Ilagan City, Isabela, held before the total lockdown due to the pandemic, Beauty Care (representing Region IV-A, SDO Dasmariñas, and Paliparan III Senior High School) secured 11th place (2020).
- **Tech-Voc Day** is celebrated to showcase accomplishments and activities, bringing together parents and learners. The event features discussions on significant topics, including TESDA NC II assessment and certification, as well as work immersion opportunities outlined in DepEd Order No. 30, s. 2017, and DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2018. Additionally, other activities include school-based Technolympics and the awarding of winners, highlighting the achievements of students in various technical-vocational fields.
- The **TESDA NC II Assessment and Certification program** certifies students' technical proficiency for three consecutive years (SY 2017-2018; SY 2018-2019; SY 2019-2020). The school produced 477 students who were certified by TESDA with the following data: EIM NC II with 52 students, EPAS NC II with 63 students, Cookery NC II with 119 students, BPP NC with 98 students, FBS NC II with 49 students, Hairdressing NC II with 36 students, Wellness “Hilot” Massage NC II with 24 students, and CSS NC II with 36 students. Following the release of the TESDA circular regarding the Enhanced

Community Quarantine (ECQ) due to the worldwide pandemic, those slated for March 2020 onward were canceled.

- **Work Immersion programs** is part of the K to 12 curriculum that provide real-world industry experience and employment opportunities through partnerships with industry stakeholders. These include placements in restaurants and fast food chains like Pizza Hut, Bread Talk, Barrio Fiesta, Savory, Tasa Mia, Yaki Mix for CBF students; Mary Pauline Salon owned by one of our teachers, and spas for BHW students and collaborations with Meralco, One-Meralco Foundation and Certified By Meralco contractors for EIM students; and Artesyn Technologies (formerly Emerson and ASTEC), CAPARAL Furniture & Appliances and leading electronics repair shops in the community for the EPAS students.
- Through the provision of **employment** opportunities, the work immersion program improves students' employability after graduation. Students who perform well throughout their training are frequently hired by industry partners, particularly those who choose for direct employment. After graduating, some students are also provided with part-time jobs.

Government expectations for SHS graduates are quite evident at our school because K to 12 TVL learners are equipped with job-ready skills and certified by TESDA as NC II passers, making them prepared for immediate employment. As a result of the collaborations as well as productive engagements with the industries, and establishments. TVL teachers were awarded the division's Gawad Pansangay Tagamasid in 2018 and 2019. They met the requirements of being multiple NC II and TM 1 holders, an accredited competency assessor, and producing at least 50% of NC II passers among the enrolled populations.

In response to the challenges posed by COVID-19, Project TSERA E2E was integrated into the School Learning Continuity Plan for SY 2020-2021 and was presented during the school improvement planning session led by the new school head. To support the Modular Distance Learning (MDL), the Division initiated the creation of learning activity sheets and self-learning materials/modules, with teachers serving as authors. These efforts aimed to ensure that students continued to receive quality education despite the pandemic, providing them with the necessary resources to learn effectively from home. During the City of Dasmariñas Research Educators' Assembly (CDREAM) in 2021, a research study titled "*Comparative Analysis of Curriculum Exit Paths for First and Second Batches of SHS-TVL Online Graduates: Initial Inputs to Localized Policy Guidelines on Project: TSERA-E2E*" was conducted by Francis Factura (main author), and Herma Vejerano (co-author). Based on the findings and recommendations of this study, **significant innovations** have been introduced to address the four (4) Curriculum Exit pathways for all Senior High School students. These four Curriculum Exits will now be *central to the development of localized policy guidelines for Project: TSERA-E2E*, ensuring that the framework is adaptable, practical, and applicable in both face-to-face learning environments and during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The research recommends a flexible approach to learning and curriculum design that can accommodate the diverse needs of students, whether in traditional or online settings. The study also highlights the importance of collaboration between the school and parents in supporting the educational development of students. Together, they will guide learners in selecting the most appropriate Curriculum Exit pathway, based on individual preferences and skillsets. The updated program will now be known as **Project: TSERA-E2E Version 2.0**, reflecting its enhanced framework and expanded focus to better support the diverse needs of students as they transition from enrolment, education to employment.